

A Review on Impact of Visual Merchandising Elements on Consumer Response

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Abstract

Visual Merchandising plays a vital role in influencing consumer perception, emotion and purchase behavior in retail environment. This review study examines the impact of key visual merchandising elements like window display, store layout, lighting, colour scheme, signage, on consumer response including attitude, attention, impulse buying behavior, and purchase intention. The findings reveal that visual merchandising significantly enhances store attractiveness, positively influence consumer emotions, and increase the likelihood of purchase decisions. Elements like window display and in-store ambience were found to be making strong impact on consumer attention and impulse buying, while store layout and signage influenced ease of navigation and overall shopping satisfaction. It has become necessary for retailers to ensure that a strong impact on customers through visual merchandising because competition in the market is high and retailers are also ready to make investment and spend money on visual merchandising to attract customers. Visual merchandising is considered as a tool that is used by majority of retailers in this competitive market. This work has examined the influence of visual merchandising, store layout, and in-store display of products, window display, and promotional signage on the consumer response.

Keywords: Visual Merchandising Elements, retail strategies, Shopping Experience, Consumer Behavior, Consumer Response.

Introduction

In present time, shopping being a necessity has turned into an adventure for majority of customers. It is considered more as an experience, and as an opportunity to celebrate. Visual merchandising is everything that a customer sees in the market, exterior and interior of the shop, it creates a positive image in the minds of the customer regarding the business resulting in interest, attention, desire and ultimately an action taken by the customer. Visual merchandising plays a vital role to attract customers of distinct sections to purchase a product. VM include presentation of the product including other important features creating the overall atmosphere of the store. The main goal of visual merchandising is creating a desire among the customer to purchase the product. VM is offered through exterior and interior presentation of product to customers. Hence, the art of visual merchandising deals significantly with creation and delivering of comfortable ambience for probable customers. Overed throughout these years, this is the reason why there are so many stores, mainly in merchandising, it has developed strategies about how to attain attention of customers and their loyalty from the targeted market. Suppliers must consider and keep evaluating their products, its price, promotion, places and people for having market differentiation. This is the reason scholars like to identify the impact of elements of visual merchandising of retail store on attention and loyalty of customers. An attempted has been made by this work to show that visual merchandising elements like window display, store layout, lighting and colour, and interior design of the store make positive influence on attention and loyalty of customers. VM is considered as a strategy by marketing professionals for boosting and creating a substantial influence on buying behavior and loyalty of customers. Any store designing its layout for the place as per the interest of their targeted market, it must hold the attention and a possibility of making purchases (**Abad, Celeridad & Soltes, 2019**). Visual merchandising includes strategic displaying of the products designed by retailers to attract their customers, attain their attention and for motivating them to make purchases, and it is considered as one of the most effective strategies to achieve their goals. Conventionally, visual merchandising was being used in physical retail spaces, where layout of the store window display, colour schemes and lighting work together for creating an appealing experience of shopping. However, with the growing digital commerce, visual merchandising has gone through a considerable transformation and has become essential in online retailing as well as initiatives of digital marketing. Uniformity in visual merchandising across digital and physical environment has become vital with the moving multichannel retail system. E on digital platform or through physical store, customer is demanding flawless brands.

VM can go ultimately beyond just simple enhancement. VM develops emotional bonds, modify the perceptions of customers, and also increase loyalty of customers. Brands innovating and stay aware of such emotional triggers would be positioned in a better way thriving in a competitive environment of retailing as it keeps changing (**Arun & Satsangi, 2025**). Visual merchandising is known as a tool utilised by retailers to achieve the attention of the customers as well as during unplanned purchasing. It is a presentation of brand in the store. Anything and everything seen by the customer, either inside or outside the store creating a positive influence on the minds of the customers is visual merchandising. The strategic role played by visual merchandising is communicating the brand to customers and the offers to similar or target customers in the market. It also differentiates the brand and its products from other brands that are available in the market. Perception of customers regarding visual merchandising can temper their interest or can motivate to explore the merchandise available in the store. Information about the brand product through visual merchandising can add to cognitive understand of customers regarding visual merchandising, optimising the sales as well as profits. Tools of VM are fixtures, colours, lighting, signage and aroma of the store (**Azhagan & Mohamed, 2020**). World of customers of full of ambience, they react differently to the visuals as well as sensations around them; while taking entry in the store, they focus on the messages or sometime even disregard them. However, customers make judgement for themselves by adapting the idea communicated to them through certain stimulus like visual merchandising displays matching with the desire, experience and biases of an individual (**Kudeshia & Mittal, 2016**). In order to frame with experience of customers, visual merchandising has appeared as an essential element, it also makes impact on buying decisions of customers. It is no longer just enough to display attractive products, instead, creating a mesmerising and involving buying atmosphere to match the preferences of customers. Layout of the store and aesthetics make significant influence on the shopping experience and preferences of customers. Gender difference make impact on effectiveness of merchandising, while age was not found to be making any impact. In order to stay competitive in the market, retailers need to integrate, AI driven strategies, augmented reality (AR) and interactive displays for improving involvement. Sustainable practices such as energy efficient lighting, eco-friendly material can assist in boosting the reputation of the brand. Businesses adapting the requirement of customers, embracing innovation and creating the seamless experience strengthening loyalty of customer, improving perception of brand, and long-term profitability (**Chandrabose & Dharshan, 2025**).

Literature Review

Gagarin et al. (2025) stated that a significant influence is made by visual merchandising on the consumer response and their buying behavior. Product display, signage, packaging and layout of the store are considered as proven effective elements that drives customer engagement and make impact on their purchase decisions. Among these elements, store layout, and packaging have appeared as the highly influencing elements that enhance experience of customers and purchase intention. Sales can be boosted by retailers and improve the level of customer satisfaction by optimising cleanliness in store, create engaging displays and by using innovative design of packaging. They must prioritize the cleanliness and layout of the store for creating the welcoming environment as well as organized shopping experience. Invest time in visually appealing and reusable packaging to improve recognition of brands and loyalty of customers. They must ensure that signage is clear and readable, need to be placed to guide effectively to customers. It is recommended to future retailers to consider the significance of elements of visual merchandising like ambience, and organized display of products to create influencing retail strategies.

Jaini et al. (2022) revealed that the concept of visual merchandising is essential to provoke internal emotions of consumers for making impulsive buying. The result suggests a conceptual framework for future research for investigating impulsive buying behavior of customers in distinct retailers stored in different regions. Moreover, an understanding is provided by the analyses for retailers to put emphasis on the particular factors of visual merchandising for increasing the attention of customers to walk-in the store and make indirect influence on their buying decisions. The findings would be proved advantageous for the retailers in designing their visual merchandising as per the interest of customers. On the basis of adaptation of “stimulus-response-organism” paradigm, a proposed conceptual framework is proposed by this work to explain the association of elements of VM, positive response of customers, and their impulsive buying behavior.

Mishra & Mishra (2022) highlighted that retail industry these days is facing strict competition in the market. There are many strong branded as well as non-branded players in the market, for example fashion apparel. In this industry, there is not much different in terms of product. The only differentiation that can be done by the retailer or marketer is display of their product. Here, an important role is played by visual merchandising as a marketing of the product. VM of retail stores must support the aspects where they are supposed to be good. They should also work on other dimensions as well which they do not qualify as every dimension is essential in terms of

VM. Visual merchandising is a key buying. If a retail store falls short of any such dimension that are mentioned can make impact on customer, ultimately impulse buying would not happen. Window display as a dimension helping visual merchandiser to attract customers, it is an element helping customers to stay longer in the store. The longer the time customer stays in the store, more they will purchase. Therefore, the atmosphere of the retail store needs to be the best and attractive to make customers feel comfortable. There needs to have some siting arrangement as well for children as well as senior customers.

Enock & Srinivasan (2025) stated that arrangement of products and promotional signage are highly influencing factors of VM, it makes significant impact on planned as well as impulse buying. It is revealed by the data that product arrangement is highly influencing in organized retail environment, where a good is presented in a well-structured manner can help in enhancing the experience of shopping and can also motivate customers to make planned as well as impulsive buying. On the other hand, promotional signage plays a vital role that triggers impulsive purchasing by drawing attention towards offers, discount, and other special promotional activities. The findings of the study recommends that retailers need to prioritise promotional signage and product arrangement in order to maximise their influence on behavior of consumers. As shown in the study, visual merchandising offers important way of differentiating physical stores by improving the experience of shopping and motivating planned and impulsive buying both. Tailored approach of visual merchandising must be adopted by retailers, considering particular preferences and requirements of target audience.

Raja & Devi (2023) revealed that visual merchandising as a concept has its roots from the days of barter system. Progressively with the arrival of organized system of retailing the appearance of visual merchandising has got its mark. VM assist consumers to have best experience of shopping. Store is just like a theatre for visual merchandiser. The walls as well as floor of store is just like a stage for them. The visual communication, lighting, and fixtures make a set of stage plays a character of the show. It is a proven fact that response of customers towards visual merchandising can be different for different demographics.

Randhawa & Saluja (2017) found that the significance of visual merchandising in India has ignored, but now it is catching the hopes of youth and is assisting merchandisers in jumping the hurdle of attracting customers towards the store. A major role is paid by visual merchandising in retail sector. It is a silent technique selling helping in reduction of employee mix and increase return on per square feet and also help to reduce marketing budget. This profession and activity include the development of floor plans and three-dimensional display for maximization of sales. Store layout is an impactful element that maintains thriving business

helping the advancement of sales and eventually profits. Effective layout of store motivates customers to shop by viewing wide-ranging variety of merchandise. Some of the common form of store layout are grid layout, racetrack and free form layout. Positive and impulsive buying experience of customer make contribution in the establishment of store loyalty and perceived value of customers along with satisfaction that influence future decisions of making purchases. Impulsive purchase decisions of customers can be influence by effective practices of visual merchandising.

Rema & Deepchand (2018) stated that VM is being adopted increasingly these days by retailers to attract customers towards their store. In the highly competitive market, retailers must develop an exciting design of the store with inventive techniques of merchandising to make customers attracted to the store and visit it, it would improve experience of shopping, eventually increase the sales. An analysis was conducted about various techniques of visual merchandising that are being used by the retailers at their retail outlets with reference to food products and assess its influence on buying decisions of customers. It is revealed that display of product, well-designed layout of the store, window display, ambience of the store, lightings and wall decoration, accessibility of the products, and visibility from shelves, colourful assortments are some of the main elements of visual merchandising driving customers make purchasing at the retail store. Retailers must concentrate on the assortment of products for increasing the attention of customers towards the product that could make direct impact on the rise of sales. Proper layout of the stores with well-planned design and good space to help customers more and explore properly simplifies the shopping process and improve the experience as well as reduce the time of picking the liked and right product without wasting time and effort. Therefore, store must concentrate on designing and planning the layout of the store in order to increase the visibility as well as accessibility of the product. Frequently changing the window display with information of the product would assist customers to learn regarding seasonal merchandising in the store, thus increase the knowledge of choice that are available to customers. Increased ambience of store with the assistance of lighting and music can improve the engagement of customers further.

Sivakumar, Jayasingh & Johnson (2023) highlighted that visual merchandising is a vital aspect of physical as well as online establishment of retailing as it makes substantial influence on consumer behavior. In online setting of retailing, VM takes the form of online visual merchandising cues like image of the product, description of the product, videos, and design of the website. All these factors are important to attract customers, increase their involvement, and also drive sales. A digital commerce is India is growing every day; retailers and marketers

need to understand the main elements that influence online sale. There is a need to ensure that online experience of shopping is visually attractive and appealing providing customers with all the information that they require before making any purchase decisions. This also include making investment ion high-quality of photography of products, using interactive videos of the product, and incorporation of user-friendly website designing and navigation. The market of digital commerce is growing, thus, retailers must make emphasis on online visual merchandising in order to stay competitive in the marker and for driving sales. Understanding of key elements making influence on consumer behavior is important to become successful in online retail space.

Soomro, Kaimkhani & Iqbal (2017) revealed that visual merchandising is a technique to make the brand attractive visually and highlights the unique features of the product as well as of the store. Specialised marketers are hired by brands who concentrate on visually improving the brand and providing a good shopping experience to customers. A substantial influence is made by visual merchandising on buying behavior of consumers and it also increases the footfall at the store. It has been observed that customers get attracted towards the store that look eye catching and attractive, resulting in impulsive buying as well. It is signified by the study that if the layout of any store is bad then it would make negative influence on overall experience of the customer. VM is considered as a technique which is used for the attainment of competitive advantage. Customers like to visit and shop from that store where they get attention. Visual merchandising is being used by retailers to attract more and more customers towards their store. Getting the attention of customers is very important for the managers of store to improve their number of sales. Strategies of visual merchandising are used by retailers to communicate with customers and to keep them visit their store again and again.

Thomas, Louise & Vipinkumar (2018) highlighted that visual merchandising can be considered as a silent salesperson, as it does not speak but effectively convey the message to customers appealing to make a purchase. To fulfil the changing expectations of customers, marketers must put high emphasis on presenting their merchandising. Marketers need to understand the significance of expectations of customers providing them the right environment. When customers are exposed to such visual stimuli, they are more likely to make buying decisions. It is suggested that such practices of visual merchandising serve as a stimulus provoking a desire and motivate customers to make buying decisions when entering the store, it makes significant impact on impulsive buying decisions of customers. In-store browsing is found to be making positive impact on impulsive buying tendency of customers and also make positive influence on positive feelings of customer. Retailers must use the findings in order to

increase their sale and innovate new tricks in terms of display. As window display makes high influence on impulsive buying of customers, it also increases the foot fall at the store, eventually improve the store experience. Retailers must use these dimensions of visual merchandising in a creative manner. It is revealed that effectiveness and usefulness of visual merchandising must be used to understand the impulsive buying behavior of customers.

Conclusion

This analytical study examines the impact of visual merchandising elements on consumer response and confirms that visual merchandising plays a decisive role in shaping consumer perception, emotions and purchase behavior. Elements such as window display, store layout, colour scheme, signage, product arrangement and in-store ambience make significant impact on customer buying behavior, store image and overall experience of shopping. The findings indicate that effective visual merchandising not only attracts customers into the store but also encourage longer store visits and enhance purchase intention. It is revealed that customers respond positively to well-coordinated and aesthetically appealing visual merchandising, which creates a strong first impression and stimulates impulsive buying. Visual cues help customers process information quickly, reduce perceived shopping efforts, and increase product visibility, thereby facilitating informed purchase decisions. Moreover, visual merchandising contributes to building brand identity, and differentiation in highly competitive retail environment, enabling retailers to communicate value and quality without extensive verbal communication.

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